

Dipole Moments and UV Spectra of some Long-chain Molecules

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About one hundred compounds with long-chain molecular structure have been prepared (most of them are new). The dipole moments of four α,ω -bis(*p*-methoxyphenylthio)alkanes and five α,ω -bis(*p*-methoxyphenylsulphonyl)alkanes have been determined to find the effect of chain-length. In the case of the sulphones, the observed values are compared with the values calculated for free rotation around all bonds intervening the end dipoles. The uv spectra of some 1,2-(distyrylsulphonyl)ethanes, and a number of α,ω -bis(arylsulphonyl)- and α,ω -bis(aryloxy)alkanes have been recorded to examine the applicability of the principle of chromophore additivity.

Long-chain molecules have some unique structural features. The possibility of coiling up of such molecules exists and the intramolecular van der Waals forces can become increasingly greater with increasing chain-length. The properties of homologous compounds of the type $X(CH_2)_nX$ are therefore of interest on account of the mutual interaction of the partial dipoles through the chain and across the space. This subject has been studied by many investigators¹. In the present work the dipole moments of a series of α,ω -bis(*p*-methoxyphenylthio)alkanes (1) and α,ω -bis(*p*-methoxyphenylsulphonyl)alkanes (2) have been determined with a

view to finding the effect of chain-length on them. The uv spectra of α,ω -bis(styrylsulphonyl)alkanes (3), α,ω -bis(arylsulphonyl)alkanes (4) and α,ω -bis(aryloxy)alkanes (5) were also recorded to find whether

these molecules with two insulated chromophoric systems have molecular extinction coefficients which

are twice those of the corresponding molecules containing only one such chromophoric system.

Results and Discussion

Melting point data of α,ω -bis(arylthio)alkanes and α,ω -bis(aryloxy)alkanes are given in Tables 1 and 2, respectively.

The dipole moments of α,ω -bis(*p*-methoxyphenylthio)alkanes (1) and α,ω -bis(*p*-methoxyphenylsulphonyl)alkanes (2) are given in Table 3. The moments of the sulphides show little variation with chain-length, while in the case of sulphones, there is a progressive increase in the moment with increase in chain-length. An exact analysis of these moments is very complex, as there are a number of group moments acting in the molecules and the angles at which they act are also not known with certainty. A qualitative examination can, however, be made.

For the α,ω -bis(*p*-methoxyphenylsulphonyl)alkanes, the partial dipole is *p*-methoxyphenylsulphonyl group. An understanding of the dipole moment of this group can be had from the moment of *p*-methoxyphenyl methyl sulphone itself. Regarding this moment, a knowledge of two parameters is important: (i) whether it includes any interaction moment from the possible conjugative interaction of the MeO and SO₂Me groups across the benzene ring, and (ii) the angles at which the moments of MeO and

TABLE 1—MELTING POINTS* (°C) OF α,ω -BIS(ARYLTHIO)ALKANES**, $R.C_6H_4S.(CH_2)_n.S.C_6H_4R$ (I) and α,ω -BIS(ARYLSULPHONYL)ALKANES, $R.C_6H_4SO_2.(CH_2)_n.SO_2.C_6H_4R$ (II)

R	Compd. (I)						Compd. (II)					
	n=2	n=3	n=4	n=5	n=8	n=10	n=2	n=3	n=4	n=5	n=8	n=10
H	67-69 ^a	-	86-87 ^b	-	81-83 ^c	85-87 ^d	180-81 ^e	126-28 ^f	120-21	813-8	119 21	71-73
<i>o</i> -Cl	82-84	-	94-96	-	81-82	-	174-76	9 -101	164-65	-	101-03	92-94
<i>p</i> -Cl	94-95	39-40	70-71	50-52	78-79	90-92	257-59 ^g	177-79	184-86	137-39	132-34	128-30
<i>o</i> -OCH ₃	82-84	60-61	128-29	54-56	60-61	41-43	179-81	119-21	155-57	97-99	101-02	73-75
<i>p</i> -OCH ₃	108-09	-	104-05	50-51	99-100	102-103	203-05	123-24	165-67	92-93	107-08	109 10

* Lit. m.p. (°C) (reference in parentheses): ^a68.5(8), ^b87.6 - 89.1(9), ^c83, ^d85(10), ^e180 - 81(8), ^f127 - 28(11), ^g255(12).

** All the new compounds gave satisfactory C and H analyses.

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SO₂Me groups act with reference to their axes of rotation. Using Fuchs' equation²³ and the dipole moment of methyl phenyl sulphone (4.66 D)²⁴, methyl *m*-chlorophenyl sulphone (4.33 D)²⁴ and chlorobenzene (1.57 D)⁶, the angle which the moment of SO₂CH₃ group makes with its axis of rotation was estimated to be 42°. Calculation of the same from the moments of methyl *m*-bromophenyl sulphone (4.35 D)²⁴ and the group

It may, therefore, be concluded that the conjugative interaction between the MeO and SO₂CH₃ groups is not appreciable.

The direction along which the moment of methyl *p*-methoxyphenyl sulphone acts (with reference to its 1-4 axis) cannot be fixed with any definiteness because the two groups are continuously rotating around the 1-4 axis of the benzene nucleus. Hence it is not possible to calculate the dipole moments of α,ω -bis(*p*-methoxyphenylsulphonyl)alkanes along the lines used for α,ω -dihaloalkanes²⁵ where the two group moments rotate at a constant angle.

In the case of α,ω -bis(*p*-methoxyphenylsulphonyl)alkanes, assuming free rotation around all the bonds intervening the two end dipoles, the following equation can, however, be used,

$$\mu^2 = 2\mu_1^2 + 2\mu_2^2 + 4\mu_1\mu_2 \cos\alpha \cos\beta - 2 \cos^2(180-\theta) (2\mu_1\mu_2 \cos\alpha \cos\beta + \mu_1^2 \cos^2\alpha + 2\mu_2^2 \cos^2\beta)$$

where μ is the moment of (*p*-MeO.C₆H₄.SO₂)₂(CH₂)_n, μ_1 the moment of OMe, μ_2 the moment of SO₂CH₃, θ the carbon valence angle and α and β are the angles which the moments of OMe and SO₂CH₃ make with the 1-4 axis of the benzene ring, respectively. The calculated and observed moments at 30 and 50° are given in Table 4.

TABLE 2—MELTING POINTS (°C) OF α,ω -DIARYLOXYALKANES*, (CH₂)_n (O.C₆H₄R)₂

R	n=2	n=3	n=4	n=5	n=10
H	94-96 ^a	59-60 ^b	97-98 ^c	46-47 ^d	83-85 ^e
<i>o</i> -Cl	101-02 ^f	79-80	83-84	40-41	65-67
<i>p</i> -Cl	130-31	119-20	102-03	57-58	89-90
<i>o</i> -OMe	135-36 ^g	119-10 ^h	95-96	93-94	82-83
<i>p</i> -OMe	145-47 ⁱ	82 83 ^j	142-43	98-99	126-28
<i>o</i> -NO ₂	165-67 ^k	111-12 ^l	122-23 ^m	82-83 ⁿ	76-77
<i>m</i> -NO ₂	135-37 ^a	116-18	130-32 ^p	88-89	-
<i>p</i> -NO ₂	146-48	126-28	143-45	97-98	80-81

*Compounds for which no references are given are new, and gave satisfactory C and H analyses; lit. m.p. (°C) (reference in parentheses): ^a97.5-99(13), ^b61 (14), ^c97-98(15), ^d48(14), ^e85(16), ^f103-04(17), ^g139-40, ^h111(18), ⁱ148-50, ^j84-85(19), ^k167-68(20), ^l112-12.5, ^m124-24.5, ⁿ83-83.5, ^p76.5-77(21), ^q139(22).

TABLE 3—POLARISATION DATA OF α,ω -BIS(*p*-METHOXYPHENYLTHIO)ALKANES, (*p*-CH₃O.C₆H₄S)₂(CH₂)_n, and α,ω -BIS(*p*-METHOXYPHENYLSULPHONYL)ALKANES, (*p*-CH₃O.C₆H₄SO₂)₂(CH₂)_n

n	α	αP_2 ml	R _D ml	μ D
Sulphides				
4	1.218	0.248	260.6	99.8
5	1.172	0.264	263.3	102.8
8	1.082	0.203	288.1	118.7
10	1.074	0.216	305.5	128.0
Sulphones				
3	6.117	0.244	942.0	95.1
3 ^a	5.722	0.269	903.8	95.1
4	6.106	0.236	984.5	100.6
4 ^a	5.742	0.270	948.2	100.6
5	6.300	0.212	1041.7	104.4
5 ^a	5.892	0.243	998.5	104.4
8	6.316	0.163	1157.1	119.1
8 ^a	5.887	0.205	1104.0	119.1
10	6.181	0.136	1207.2	128.4
10 ^a	5.761	0.177	1152.9	128.4

^aTemperature of measurement, 50°.

moments of Br (1.55 D)⁶ and SO₂CH₃ (4.66 D)²⁴ gave a value of 44°. A similar calculation from the moments of methyl *m*-nitrophenyl sulphone (4.80 D)²⁴, nitrobenzene (3.95 D)⁶ and methyl phenyl sulphone (4.66 D) gave the angle as 39°. The average of the three values (42°) was taken as the dipole angle of SO₂CH₃. The dipole angle of the OMe group was taken⁶ as 75°. Using the above data, the dipole moment of methyl *p*-methoxyphenyl sulphone was calculated to be 5.05 D. It is not very much different from the observed value, 5.16 D.

TABLE 4—DIPOLE MOMENT OF THE ALKANES *p*-MeO.C₆H₄.SO₂)₂(CH₂)_n

Alkane n	μ obs (D)		μ Calc D
	30°	50°	
2 ^a	—	—	—
3	6.49	6.54	7.06
4	6.63	6.70	7.12
5	6.83	6.88	7.14
8	7.18	7.22	7.15
10	7.34	7.36	7.15

^aInsoluble.

Had the dipole moment of the compound for which n=2 been available, it would have enhanced the value of the data given in Table 4, but unfortunately it could not be determined due to the insolubility of the compound in benzene and dioxane. The increasing moment with chain-length is due to the greater freedom of intramolecular rotation. This view is substantiated by the fact that the moments at 50° are higher than the corresponding moments at 30°. Freedom of intramolecular rotation increases with the increase of temperature. With increasing chain-length the tendency of the molecule to bend or coil also increases, which in turn, leads to the polarisation of more bonds of the molecule in the vicinity of the primary dipoles. Taking this factor into consideration, the calculated values can be said to be in satisfactory agreement with the observed values.

Ultraviolet spectra: Molecules with two chromophoric systems, separated by one or more saturated atoms, or *meta*-oriented about a benzene ring, absorb light of nearly the same wavelength as a molecule containing only one such chromophoric system, but the intensity of the light absorbed is approximately twice that of the latter²⁶. It was considered to be of interest whether this principle of additivity holds good for sulphones of the type $\text{ArCH}=\text{CH}.\text{SO}_2.\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2.\text{CH}=\text{CH}.\text{Ar}$ and $\text{ArSO}_2(\text{CH}_2)_n\text{SO}_2\text{Ar}$ in view of the strong inductive effect of the sulphonyl group. The spectral data are given in Tables 5 and 6. The α,ω -bis(styrylsulphonyl)ethanes (Table 5) exhibit

the principle of additivity to a remarkable extent in respect of the molar extinction coefficients. No significance is attached for differences less than 5% because such differences can arise from experimental errors. In Table 6, the comparison is between monosulphones ArSO_2CH_3 and disulphones $\text{ArSO}_2(\text{CH}_2)_n\text{SO}_2\text{Ar}$. When $n=2$, the molar extinction coefficient of the disulphone is more than twice that of the monosulphone except in the case of the methoxy compounds. For compounds where n is greater than 2, ϵ_{max} is nearly twice the value of the monosulphone. The higher extinction coefficient of the first member ($n=2$) is presumably due to the mutual induction of the sulphonyl groups which may become negligible when n is greater than 2. In the methoxy compounds conjugation exists between CH_2O and SO_2CH_3 groups through the styryl moiety, reducing the positive charge on the sulphonyl group, which in turn reduces the mutual induction between the sulphonyl groups.

In Table 7 are compared the spectra of aryl methyl ethers and α,ω -bis(aryloxy)alkanes. The 1L_b and 1L_a bands²⁷, which are shown by benzene derivatives, are also shown by the compounds listed in Table 7. Only the *m*-nitro compounds show an additional band at 269 nm. It is presumably due to the $\text{O}_2\text{N}.\text{C}_6\text{H}_4$ partial chromophore²⁸. The principle of additivity of the molar extinction coefficients holds good for both the bands of *o*-chloro, *o*-methoxy, *o*-nitro and *m*-nitro compounds. It is worthy of note that all these are *ortho*- or *meta*-substituted compounds. For the other compounds the additivity principle holds good for the low intensity 1L_b band but not for the high intensity 1L_a band. It may be borne in mind that the aryloxy group keeps rotating freely around the $\text{ArO}-\text{CH}_2$ bond. There is also the possibility of the molecules bending and the α,ω -aryloxy groups coming close to each

TABLE 5—UV SPECTRA OF METHYL STYRYL SULPHONES, $\text{Ar}.\text{CH}=\text{CH}.\text{SO}_2\text{CH}_3$ (I) and α,ω -BIS(STYRYLSULPHONYL)ETHANES, $\text{Ar}.\text{CH}=\text{CH}.\text{SO}_2.\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2.\text{SO}_2.\text{CH}=\text{CH}.\text{Ar}$ (II)

Ar	Compd. (I)	Compd. (II)
	λ_{max} (nm) (ϵ_{max})	λ_{max} (nm) (ϵ_{max})
C_6H_5	263 (20400)	268 (39700)
<i>o</i> -Cl. C_6H_4	263 (17500)	267 (35600)
<i>p</i> -Cl. C_6H_4	268 (24800)	275 (48600)
<i>o</i> -NO ₂ . C_6H_4	235 (16200)	236 (33000)
<i>m</i> -NO ₂ . C_6H_4	251 (27500)	255 (53800)
<i>p</i> -NO ₂ . C_6H_4	289 (16800)	288 (33400)
3,4-CH ₂ O ₂ . C_6H_3	317 (13500)	322 (26900)
	282 (11000)	285 (21600)
	235 (14000)	237 (26900)
3,4-Cl ₂ . C_6H_3	308 (2200)	309 ^a (4100)
	268 (25800)	274 (49900)

^aInflexion.

TABLE 6—UV SPECTRA (nm) OF ARYL METHYL SULPHONES, $\text{R}.\text{C}_6\text{H}_4.\text{SO}_2\text{CH}_3$ (I) AND α,ω -BIS(ARYLSULPHONYL)ALKANES, $\text{R}.\text{C}_6\text{H}_4.\text{SO}_2(\text{CH}_2)_n\text{SO}_2.\text{C}_6\text{H}_4.\text{R}$ (II)

R	Compd. (I)	Compd. (II)					
		$n=2$	$n=3$	$n=4$	$n=5$	$n=8$	$n=10$
	λ_{max} (ϵ_{max})						
H	264 (1000)	266 (2200)	265 (2000)	265 (1950)	265 (1950)	265 (2050)	265 (2000)
<i>o</i> -Cl	217 (7500)	220 (19000)	218 (15300)	218 (15200)	218 (15100)	218 (15200)	218 (15100)
	273 (1500)	275 (3300)	274 (2950)	273 (2900)	—	273 (2950)	273 (3000)
	222 (7600)	221 (17100)	223 (14600)	223 (14600)	—	223 (14900)	223 (14800)
<i>p</i> -Cl	264 (580)	265 (1350)	265 (1200)	264 (1150)	265 (1150)	265 (1100)	264 (1100)
	229 (15800)	231 (34200)	231 (32000)	230 (31800)	229 (31600)	229 (32400)	229 (31800)
<i>o</i> -OCH ₃	284 (3900)	285 (7550)	285 (7700)	285 (7600)	284 (7650)	284 (7650)	284 (7550)
	224 (7600)	225 (15200)	225 (15000)	225 (14800)	225 (14600)	225 (14900)	224 (14400)
<i>p</i> -OCH ₃	278 (730)	277 (1450)	277 (1450)	277 (1460)	278 (1400)	278 (1450)	278 (1500)
	240 (17100)	243 (34700)	243 (34600)	241 (34500)	240 (34400)	240 (34500)	240 (34600)

TABLE 7—UV SPECTRA (nm) OF ANISOLES, R.C₆H₄.OCH₃ (I) AND α,ω -BIS(ARYLOXY)ALKANES, R.C₆H₄.O.(CH₂)_n.O.C₆H₄.R (II)

R	Compd. (I)		Compd. (II)				
	λ_{\max} (ϵ_{\max})	$n=2$ λ_{\max} (ϵ_{\max})	$n=3$ λ_{\max} (ϵ_{\max})	$n=4$ λ_{\max} (ϵ_{\max})	$n=5$ λ_{\max} (ϵ_{\max})	$n=10$ λ_{\max} (ϵ_{\max})	
H	271 (1750) 220 (7100)	271 (3250) 221 (16350)	271 (3500) 221 (16300)	271 (3500) 221 (16200)	271 (3500) 221 (16300)	271 (3600) 221 (16900)	
<i>o</i> -Cl	275 (2300) 221 (7050)	275 (3800) 218 (14600)	275 (4100) 218 (15000)	276 (4450) 219 (14100)	275 (4100) 219 (14800)	276 (4000) 219 (14200)	
<i>p</i> -Cl	289 (1300) 282 (1600) 228 (10800)	288 (2600) 280 (3200) 229 (26400)	288 (2600) 280 (3250) 229 (25400)	288 (2600) 281 (3300) 229 (26100)	289 (2600) 281 (3200) 229 (24200)	289 (2600) 281 (3200) 229 (24400)	
<i>o</i> -OCH ₃	275 (2400) 226 (7000)	275 (4700) 224 (14400)	275 (4700) 225 (14400)	275 (4800) 225 (14400)	275 (4750) 225 (14300)	275 (4700) 225 (14300)	
<i>p</i> -OCH ₃	290 (2750) 226 (8400)	289 (4950) 226 (19000)	289 (4900) 226 (18300)	289 (5100) 227 (18700)	289 (5000) 227 (18000)	IS 325 (4800) 260 (6200)	
<i>o</i> -NO ₂	326 (2500) 260 (3400)	— — — 323 (4150)	326 (4900) 260 (6700)	326 (4900) 260 (6600)	325 (4900) 260 (6500)	325 (4800) 260 (6200)	
<i>m</i> -NO ₂	328 (2100) 269 (5800) 228 (10600)	323 (4150) 268 (11500) 227 (21700)	325 (4000) 268 (11100) 228 (21400)	327 (4000) 269 (11100) 228 (21300)	328 (4200) 269 (11400) 228 (21700)	— — — 309 (22700) 227 (14200)	
<i>p</i> -NO ₂	308 (11300) 228 (7800)	309 (23800) 226 (14800)	309 (22800) 227 (14300)	309 (23900) 227 (13900)	309 (23200) 227 (14100)	309 (22700) 227 (14200)	

IS=Insufficiently soluble in ethanol.

other. Coming closest can be by the parallel approach or the non-parallel approach of the α,ω -benzene rings.

In the non-parallel approach the *ortho*- and *meta*-substituents prevent the α,ω -aryloxy groups from attaining the closest possible position. Hence, the closest distance that can be attained by end-groups of the unsubstituted and *para*-substituted compounds cannot be attained by those of the *meta*-substituted compounds in the non-parallel approach. Attaining closest approach by the parallel approach is a rare possibility. Thus the intramolecular polar interactions that occur more easily in the unsubstituted and *para*-substituted compounds presumably cause the observed deviations from the expected additivity of molar extinction coefficients.

The ϵ_{\max} of the 1L_b band is not as much affected as the 1L_a band by polarity changes of the substituents in the benzene ring²⁷. So the intramolecular polar interactions, occurring in the unsubstituted and *para*-substituted compounds, are seen to affect the intensity of the 1L_a band only perceptibly.

Experimental

Methyl styryl sulphones²³ and α,ω -bis(styryl-sulphonyl)ethanes⁴ were prepared by the reported methods: *methyl o-nitrostyryl sulphone*: m.p. 133–34° (Found: C, 47.6; H, 3.8. C₉H₉NO₂S calcd. for: C, 47.6; H, 4.0%); *methyl p-nitrostyryl sulphone*: m.p. 192–94° (Found: C, 47.8; H, 4.2. C₉H₉NO₂S calcd. for: C, 47.6; H, 4.0%).

α,β -Bis(aryltio)alkanes. *General method*: The appropriate thiophenol (0.022 mol) was added to a solution of KOH (0.027 mol) in ethanol (25 ml), followed by α,ω -dibromoalkane (0.01 mol). The mixture was allowed to stand for 2 h, heated on a steam-bath to complete the reaction, then diluted with water and the separated solid was washed free of alkali and recrystallised from ethanol as colourless crystals (Table 1). In the case of sulphides which were obtained as liquids, the sulphide was extracted with ether, then the ether was removed by evaporation and the sulphide was used as such for oxidation.

α,ω -Bis(arylsulphonyl)alkanes. *General method*: The sulphide was dissolved in excess of glacial

acetic acid, treated with three-fold excess of H_2O_2 (30%) and refluxed for 1 h, or, alternatively, treated with a solution of $KMnO_4$ (5–6%) and heated on a water-bath for 0.5 h. The reaction mixture was then worked up as usual. The sulphones were recrystallised from ethanol (Table 1).

α,ω -Bis(aryloxy)alkanes. *General method*: The appropriate phenol (0.008 mol) was added to a solution of KOH (0.008 mol) in ethanol and to the clear solution was added the α,ω -dibromoalkane (0.002 mol). The mixture was then refluxed for 3 h, diluted with water, allowed to stand for a few hours and the resulting solid was washed free of alkali and recrystallised from ethanol (Table 2).

Dielectric constant and density of the solutions were measured at 30°, unless stated to be at 50°, with the apparatus described earlier⁵. The solvent used was dioxane, unless stated it to be benzene. Definitions of symbols and the method of calculating the dipole moments were the same as reported earlier⁶. Dielectric constant values of dioxane were taken as 2.1973 and 2.1755, and the density values as 1.0224 and 0.99958, at 30° and 50° respectively. The dielectric constant and density of benzene at 30° were taken as 2.2629 and 0.86834, respectively. In the case of liquids the molar refraction (R_D) was calculated from the density and refractive index measurements. In the case of solids, R_D was estimated from bond refractions⁷.

The uv spectral measurements were made with a Hilger and Watts UVISPECK spectrophotometer. The solvent used was 95% ethanol.

References

1. C. P. SMYTH and W. S. WALLS, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1933, 1, 200; J. A. A. KETELAAR and N. VAN MEURS, *Rec. Trav. Chim.*, 1957, 76, 437; H. J. G. HAYMAN and I. ELIEZER, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1958, 28, 890; H. B. THOMSON and S. L. HANSON, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1961, 65, 1065; R. P. SMITH and J. J. RASMUSSEN, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, 83, 3785; M. T. ROGERS, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1957, 61, 1442; CL. BEGUIN and T. GAUMANN, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1958, 41, 1376; J. D. MORRISON and J. M. ROBERTSON, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, 980, 987, 993, 1001; R. GANE and C. K. INGOLD, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 2153; L. A. WILES and E. C. BAUGHAN, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 933; L. A. WILES, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 996; R. GANE and C. K. INGOLD, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 1594; M. M. DONDON, *Compt. Rend.*, 1954, 238, 1223; M. L. PETRANKER and Z. WELWART, *Compt. Rend.*, 1953, 236, 2078; R. ROMETZCH, A. MARXER and K. MIRSCHER, *Helv. Chem. Acta*, 1951, 34, 1611; F. H. WESTHEIMER and M. W. SHOOKHOFF, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1939, 61, 555; G. GEISLER and F. ASINGER, *Chem. Ber.*, 1956, 89, 1100, 1233; R. A. FULTON and W. B. LEE, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 1057; H. CRAWFORD and W. T. LITTLE, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1959, 732; T. WIELAND and H. HORNIG, *Annalen*, 1956, 600, 12; H. E. UNGNADE and R. A. SMILEY, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1956, 21, 993; H. E. UNGNADE and L. W. KISSINGER, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1957, 22, 1088; P. RAMART-LUCAS and L. LABAUNE, *Ann. Chim.*, 1931, 16, 276; P. RAMART-LUCAS and J. HOCK, *Ann. Chim.*, 1932, 17, 207; P. RAMART-LUCAS and Z. PAPADAKIS, *Ann. Chim.*, 1932, 18, 32; P. RAMART-LUCAS and P. AMAGAT, *Bull. Soc. Chim.*, 1932, 51, 965; P. RAMART-LUCAS, *Bull. Soc. Chim.*, 1943, 10, 13.
2. M. BALASUBRAMANIAN, V. BALIAH and T. R. RANGARAJAN, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, 3297.
3. V. BALIAH and M. SESHAPATHIRAO, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1959, 24, 876.
4. V. BALIAH, K. APARAJITHAN and S. PREMA, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1981, 20, 716.
5. V. BALIAH and K. GANAPATHY, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1963, 59, 1784.
6. V. BALIAH and M. UMA, *Tetrahedron*, 1963, 19, 455.
7. A. I. VOGEL, W. T. CRESSWELL, G. H. JEFFREY and J. LEICHESTER, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, 514.
8. J. HINE and W. H. BRADER, JR., *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 75, 3964.
9. E. D. AMSTUTZ, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1944, 9, 316.
10. J. V. BRAUN, *Chem. Ber.*, 1909, 42, 4545.
11. H. OTTO, *J. Prakt. Chem. (2)*, 1895, 51, 293.
12. M. KULKA, *Can. J. Chem.*, 1958, 36, 753.
13. E. L. ELIEL, C. HERRMANN and J. T. TRAXLER, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, 78, 1198.
14. TH. LIESER and G. BECK, *Chem. Ber.*, 1950, 83, 140.
15. W. REPPE, *Annalen*, 1955, 596, 124.
16. J. V. BRAUN, *Chem. Ber.*, 1909, 42, 4549.
17. R. STÖRMER and F. GOHL, *Chem. Ber.*, 1903, 36, 2874.
18. L. GATTERMANN, *Annalen*, 1907, 357, 381.
19. M. KOHN and F. WILHELM, *Monatsh. Chem.*, 1922, 43, 551.
20. A. C. COPE, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 57, 572.
21. R. JAUNIN and H. HOLL, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1958, 41, 1789.
22. E. WAGNER, *J. Prakt. Chem. (2)*, 1883, 27, 200.
23. O. FUCHS, *Z. Phys. Chem. (B)*, 1931, 14, 339.
24. K. APARAJITHAN, Ph.D. Thesis, Annamalai University, 1962.
25. C. P. SMYTH, "Dielectric Behaviour and Structure", McGraw-Hill, New York, 1955, pp. 368-370.
26. L. N. FERGUSON, "Electronic Structures of Organic Molecules", Constable and Company, London, 1952, p. 280.
27. H. H. JAFFE and M. ORCHIN, "Theory and Applications of Ultraviolet Spectroscopy", Wiley, New York, 1962.
28. V. BALIAH and R. VARADACHARI, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1989, 28, 116.